

Guodian Laozi 郭店老子

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Guodian Laozi 郭店老子 is the name given to three manuscripts inked on bamboo found during the 1993 archaeological excavation at Tomb No. 1 of the Guodian 郭店 Tombs near Jingmen 荊門, Hubei Province 湖北. These three manuscripts and the others (18 in total) found in the same tomb have been dated around the final phase of the Warring States period (453-222 BCE), approximately around 300 BCE. These three manuscripts, labeled as Manuscript A (jia 甲), B (yi 乙), and C (bing 丙), constitute the very first edition found to date of material pertaining to the textual tradition of the Daodejing 道德經 ("Classic of the Way and Virtue"), predating by more than a century the two silk manuscripts (Boshuben 帛書本) found at Mawangdui 馬王堆 in 1973. The Laozi scrolls, along with the Ziyi 緇衣 and the Wuxing 五行, represent the only manuscripts related to already known texts found within the tomb: all other manuscripts were unknown until their discovery at Guodian. The three scrolls are distinguished by different handwriting and bamboo strips, and in total they comprise around one third of the transmitted Daodejing (about 1750 characters), presenting variations from the transmitted text in the lexicon, in the division into chapters, and furthermore they lack the canonical division into the Daojing 道經 (Classic of the Way) and Dejing 德經 (Classic of the Virtue) sections. Furthermore, the three scrolls vary greatly in length from one another. Laozi A is inked on 39 bamboo strips (32.3 cm in length), B is inked on 18 strips (30.6 cm), and C is inked on 14 strips (26.5 cm). It also needs to be noted that scroll C has identical bamboo strip length, binding marks, and handwriting from another text, that the editors of the Guodian Chumu Zhujian 郭店楚墓竹簡 (The Bamboo Manuscripts from the Chu Tomb at Guodian) entitled Taiyi sheng shui 太一生水: originally, the two texts were possibly bound together. The three bundles present only one duplication among them: in fact, the second half of received chapter 64 occurs both in bundle A and bundle C, despite presenting major variations in the two occurrences. The repetition of this passage in two scrolls, together with the division into three different scrolls of material closely related to the textual tradition of the Daodejing, and the possible coexistence of another manuscript (the Taiyi sheng shui) within the same scroll with Laozi C, suggest the possibility that, at the time of their burial around the end of the 4th century BCE, the three bundles were not perceived as forming one coherent text. Content-wise, with the only exception of the 14 bamboo strips that constitute the Taiyi sheng shui, all the material inked on the three scrolls can be traced to the transmitted Daodejing, with variations both in word choice and in the order of the passages. Most of the word variations are orthographic or homophonic, yet there are few instances in which the variations lead to significant change in meaning. Above all, in Laozi A, passage 1, which corresponds to the received chapter 19: the so-called Confucian virtues (sheng 聖, sagacity; zhi 智, knowledge; ren 仁, benevolence; yi 義, propriety) are not criticized as in its received counterpart. The questions whether these scrolls represented an older or original edition of the Laozi, or a selection from a larger corpus of textual material, or even separate texts not yet perceived as a coherent whole is still open to debate. But certainly, the Guodian archaeological find has predated to 300 BCE the existence of at least the philosophical core of the Daodejing. The themes covered within the three scrolls seem to overlap, so it seems unlikely that the three separate scrolls represent selections made from a single text based on a thematic choice. One example among all, the theme of non-action (either wuwei 無為 or wangwei 亡為 on bamboo) is present and central in all three scrolls. In particular, the person of the shengren 聖人 in the Guodian Laozi is throughout connected to the principle of non-action: the adherence to this principle appears as a crucial requirement for a person to be considered wise. The shengren is described as a person characterized by the lack of desires and by the attitude of avoiding purposeful action: in the bamboo text, not only wangwei appears

eight times, but every occurrence of the word shengren is connoted by sentences with negative structure, that is, through the use of wu 無, wang 亡 or bu 不, that invoke wuwei.

Date Range: 350 BCE - 300 BCE

Region: Guodian Tomb One

Region tags: China, Hubei Province

Guodian Tomb One is located near the village of Guodian 郭店 at Jingmen 荊門 in Hubei 湖北 province. It was excavated in 1993.

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Jingmenshi Bowuguan 荊門市博物館 (ed.). 1998. Guodian Chu mu zhujian 郭店楚墓竹簡. Peking: Wenwu Press.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.colorado.edu/faculty/richter-matthias/database>

– Source 1 Description: Database of Selected Characters from Guodian and Mawangdui Manuscripts by Matthias L. Richter

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/guodian>

– Source 1 Description: Guodian Laozi in Chinese Text Project

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.daoisopen.com/guodianlaozi.html>

– Source 2 Description: Dao is open

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Bamboo

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The manuscript is stored in the Jingmenshi Bowuguan 荊門市博物館 (Museum of the city of Jingmen).

↳ Tomb

– Yes

Notes: The text has been excavated from Guodian 郭店 tomb n.1 in Jingmen 荊門, Hubei, after the tomb had been robbed at least twice in August and in mid-October 1993.

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– Specify: Jingmenshi Bowuguan 荆門市博物館 (Museum of the city of Jingmen).

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Despite the Daodejing being considered part of the so-called "Daoist Canon" of reference for Religious Daoism (Daojiao 道教), there is no evidence that the early manuscripts had similar roles.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The Guodian Laozi, as well as the transmitted Daodejing, is not written in a religious or sacred language, yet the rhymed structure together with the expressive complexity of the text (linguistically and in terms of content) affect the mysticism of the book.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Robinet (1991) claims that the poetic form of the received text suggests that it was believed that it could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition and it was therefore intended to be memorized and sung.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: With the name Guodian Laozi 郭店老子 we refer to three different scrolls of textual material that represents around one third of the transmitted Daodejing (with difference in word choice and in the order of the passages). Different versions of the text have come down to us, along different lines of transmission, as well as various other manuscripts, such as the ones excavated from Mawangdui 馬王堆 (Hunan) and Dunhuang 敦煌 (Gansu).

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The three scrolls of the Guodian Laozi are part of the Guodian corpus of bamboo manuscripts excavated from Guodian tomb n.1. Scholars believe this corpus was (part of) a private collection, propriety of the tomb owner - probably a member of the lower nobility (an “upper shi,” shangshi 上士) of the Warring States period.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: philosophical

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: none

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Guodian Laozi C 3 (corresponding to received Daodejing ch. 31) refers to funerary rites that need to be conducted for the deceased in a battle.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: There is no explicit mention of a supreme high god in the text.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: While the received text explicitly mention non-human beings such as shen 神 and gui 鬼, those chapters do not appear in the Guodian Laozi.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: None

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The word de 德, that can be translated as "virtue" has a central role both in the transmitted text and in the manuscript editions. It is important to note that while the received Daodejing strongly distances itself from the so-called Confucian virtues (sheng 聖, sagacity; zhi 智, knowledge; ren 仁, benevolence; yi 義, propriety), the same passage in the Guodian Laozi (A 1) does not refer to those virtues.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The text does not use fictive kinship terminology in reference to its readers, but uses the term mu 母 (mother) in reference to the Dao 道 itself. Guodian Laozi A 11 (corresponding to the received chapter 25) reads: 有狀混成，先天地生，清寥，獨立不亥，可以為天下母。 On the use of the word mu 母 in the context of the Daodejing textual tradition see: C. Cook 2015.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A state

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education in China has been primarily restricted to males for centuries.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text stands out against all forms of war and stresses the importance of avoiding warfare through non-action (wuwei 無為/wangwei 亡為).

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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